

Reaction of rice accessions to thrips at TRRI, Aduthurai, India. Aug 1991 and 1992.

Accession	Cross parents	Infestation (%)		Reaction ^a
		1991	1992	
BPT6038	BPT3291/ARC6650	4.2	5.0	R
BPT6881	MTU5182/IR50	5.8	7.0	R
BPT7325	MTU4870/IR50	6.9	9.0	R
KAU42-40-4-1	MO 6/Pokkali 372	5.3	7.0	R
MTU11351	IR19660-73-4/IR1416-131-5	7.6	8.2	R
RP2333-59-25	Ratna/ARC10659	9.3	9.0	R
RP2543-12874-286-1	Rasi/RP1579-38	9.8	9.0	R
RP1746-12360-340	RPA5854/RP79-9//Rasi/PTB12	9.9	10.0	R
RP2548-1702-5	ARC5723/ARC6650/ARC7328	10.2	10.5	MR
CR157-212	Vijaya/PTB21	10.5	10.7	MR
VRS100001	CNA 762260	11.1	15.0	MR
OR443-80-7	IR36/OR 127-1	12.0	12.0	MR
OR776-SSD-47	Daya/IR36	12.1	17.0	MR
RB02-111*	Samaridhi/IR8608-298	13.0	17.0	MR
R650-1817	CR157-392/OR 57-21	15.3	16.0	MR
RNR52147	IR8/Siam 29//IR8/PTB21	15.8	19.0	MR
RP2333-315-16	Ratna/ARC10659	16.3	15.0	MR
BPT6090	BPT2685/ARC5984	23.70	25.0	MS
BPT6093	BPT2685/ARC5984	28.30	27.0	MS
BPT6884	MTU5182/IR50	28.5	29.0	MS
TNAU LFR842718	Bhavani/ARC10550	28.6	25.0	MS
KAU8754	IR36/Jyothi	29.0	27.0	MS
KAU8755	IR36/Pavizham	31.0	32.2	MS
KAU8759	IR36/Annapoorna	33.7	34.5	MS
KAU8770	BR51/23332	38.9	37.0	MS
TN1 (check)	DGNG/Tsai-Yuan/Chan	89.9	90.0	S

^aR = resistant (0-10% infestation), MR = moderately resistant (11-20%), MS = moderately susceptible (21-50%), and S = susceptible (51-100%).

Integrated germplasm improvement— irrigated

Evaluation of rice varieties for lowland cultivation in Papua New Guinea

M. S. Sajjad, Agriculture and Livestock Department, Food Management Branch, Erap Research and Development Centre, P.O. Box 1984, Lae, Papua New Guinea

We evaluated introduced varieties BR12-5-5-1-1, IR19728-2-2-2-2, IR13429-196-1-20, IR46, IR54, IR4744-295-2-3, and local varieties Wantok, Tambu, and Senis under lowland field condition at Bubia during 1991.

Performance of rice varieties under lowland field condition.^a Bubia, Papua New Guinea, 1991.

Variety	Yield (t/ha)	Plant height (cm)	Productive tillers/hill (no.)	Panicle length (cm)	Grains/panicle (no.)	Panicle fertility (%)	1,000-grain wt (g)
Wantok	8.9 a	109.1 a	17.0 a	26.8 b	177.3 a	90.0 a	26.6 a
Tambu	8.8 a	102.2 b	18.0 a	27.6 a	159.0 a	91.0 a	25.2 b
Senis	6.1 b	91.7 c	14.1 b	25.5 a	119.5 d	89.0 a	26.6 a
IR19728-2-2-2-2	4.9 c	83.2 d	12.1 b	25.2 a	109.3 d	85.0 b	20.0 c
IR13429-196-1-20	8.9 a	103.3 b	17.4 a	27.9 a	148.5 b	89.5 a	21.1 c
IR46	7.9 a	108.6 a	17.4 a	23.6 a	126.3 c	90.2 a	21.3 c
IR54	8.3 a	105.0 a	16.1 a	25.0 a	118.6 d	91.0 a	25.3 b
IR4744-295-2-3	9.3 a	104.4 a	21.8 a	26.4 a	112.0 d	88.2 a	25.1 b
BR12-5-5-1-1	8.4 a	102.7 b	20.0 a	24.0 a	135.1 c	87.5 a	20.0 c

^aIn a column, figures followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

IRRN REMINDER

Reprint service. All items included in the *Rice literature update* are available at the IRRI Library and Documentation Service. Photocopies of original documents (not to exceed 50 pages) are supplied free to rice scientists of developing countries. Rice scientists elsewhere are charged US\$0.20 for each page or part of a page copied, plus postage. Payment should be in check or money order, payable to Library and Documentation Service, IRRI.

Address requests to Library and Documentation Service, IRRI, P.O. Box 933, Manila 1099, Philippines.

Fax: (63-2) 818-2087, electronic mail: IN% "postmaster@IRRI.CGNET.COM"

We transplanted 20-d-old seedlings at 2 seedlings/hill, at a plant-to-row distance of 20 cm. The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with four replications. Fertilizer was applied at 120-60-60 kg NPK/ha. All P and K and 50% N were applied basally. The remaining N was topdressed in two equal splits 20 and 40 d after transplanting. Normal cultural practices were followed during the growing period of crop.

Data on yield were recorded after harvesting a 15-m² area/variety per replication. Data on yield components were recorded for 20 plants that had no missing hills around them/variety per replication.

Varieties Wantok, Tambu, IR13429-196-1-20, IR46, IR54, IR4744-295-2-3, and BR12-5-5-1-1 yielded more than the others (see table). These varieties also had superior yield components, including grains per panicle, percent panicle fertility, and 1,000-grain weight. ■